

APPROACHES FOR WATER CONSERVATION AND REUSE IN KRAFT BASED PULP AND PAPER INDUSTRY

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Abstract: Pulp and Paper industry is notoriously jinxed for water consumption. Being connected to agricultural cycle and dependent on monsoon, the impact of water cycle is repeated year after year. Efforts have been made globally to minimize water consumption either by inducing recycle/reuse of water from various sections or by alternative raw material, modifying digestion method, altering bleaching process/technology, adopting efficient stock preparation, upgrading wastewater treatment, better housekeeping and introducing mathematical programming. Globally, average water consumption by a large scale wood based Pulp and Paper mill is 28.66m³/ton of paper while in India it is about 80-150 m³/ ton (Naidu, 2012). Inclusion of recent technological developments in various sections of the industry and its impact on water consumption has been elaborated in the paper. Further, application of mathematical tools for optimization of water usage in paper production is highlighted. Review exhibits up to 80% water conservation by wastewater treatment methods, 60% by mathematical programming tools and 50% by in-plant modifications. A case study presented for Indian pulp and paper industry investigated the effectiveness of on-site modifications and found an average reduction of 23.55 m³/ton of freshwater.

Key Words: Water conservation, Pulp and Paper Industry, Water Reuse, Industrial Wastewater Treatment, Water Pinch

[Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/>, McKinsey&Company]

1. INTRODUCTION

Paper Industry is among the basic industries which highlights literacy and development of a nation. Demand for Paper is growing worldwide despite advances in electronic media because of its requirement in various sectors mainly education, packaging and media [Figure 1.].

Figure 1. Global paper consumption growth

Global Paper Production has increased from 43.74 million tonnes in 1950 to 410.9 million tonnes in 2016 vis-à-vis, 15.3 million tonnes in India for 2016 (Confederation of European Paper Industries (CEPI), 2019; Indian Paper Manufacturers Association (IPMA), 2019). Major growth drivers of Paper industry in India are Economic growth (6.75%) and increasing literacy (75.0 % in 2016 with 8.66% increase), increasing government spending on Education, Population Growth (1.64% during 2001-2011) and higher urbanization (2.5% growth) are the other factors influencing growth of paper industry (Census, 2011; IPMA, 2019).

Despite such importance, the industry is highly water intensive. It stands third globally and second in India and Europe and 1st in US and Canada in terms of water consumption. In India, approximately 905.8 million m³ of water is consumed and 695.7 million m³ of wastewater is discharged annually by Pulp and Paper industry (Naidu, 2012). To reduce water consumption in pulp and paper industry, different methodologies and technologies have been developed by researchers and many of them are adopted in India (Table 1).

Table 1. Measures for Water Conservation by Indian Pulp and Paper Industry

Industry	Actions for water conservation	Outcome
Plant 1 located in western India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Installation of New Fiberline with Elemental Chlorine free Bleaching, Four stage bleaching with only two stage washing sequence, Oxygen delignification, four super batch reactor based digesters, Online monitoring system (Digital control system) with online Kappa analyser. 	Water consumption at 20m ³ /ton of pulp.
Plant 2 located in western India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using post oxygen back water in displacement press 	Reduction in reclaimed water consumption by 60m ³ /hr
Plant 3 located in southern India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hot water from heat exchangers used at Hot Water Elemental Chlorine Free bleaching by controlling inlet water flow and optimizing the outlet temperature. 	Freshwater consumption reduced to 100m ³ /hr from 136m ³ /hr
Plant 4 located in southern India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used back water from paper machines for displacement press pulp dilution by erecting a backwater storage tank and laying down pipes to displacement stage for pulp dilution. 	Reduced fresh water consumption by 2000 KL/day
Plant 5 located in eastern India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RO reject and cooling tower blow down from power plants returned back to reservoir for re-use in the process. 	Considerable saving in water use.
Plant 6 located in southern India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used the process condensate of the evaporation plant as sealing water for the vacuum pumps & compressors by a Mist Cooling System. 	Mill water usage had got reduced by 1050 m ³ per day.

This paper elaborates techniques developed for water conservation in the kraft pulp and paper industry. Brief overview of the industry and section wise percentage water requirement is shown in Figure 2 and Table 2

Table 2. Section Wise Water Requirement in Kraft Based Pulp and Paper Industry

Section	Percentage of total freshwater required*
Chipper House	Not required (using treated water)
Digester	8-13%
Washing and Screening	6-9%
Bleaching	5-7.5%
Paper Machine	15-17%
Soda Recovery	35-39%
Boiler	15-18%
Makeup water	5-8%

*Data collected by field visit

respectively.

Figure 2. Process flowchart of Kraft based pulp and paper industry

2. WATER CONSERVATION TECHNIQUES

These methods have been categorised as Wastewater treatment for reclamation of water, Mathematical and graphical methods, and On-site methods.

2.1 Wastewater Treatment for Reclamation of Water

Use of alum for Coagulation/flocculation results in reduction in water consumption by recovering water (Ahmad et al., 2007). RO filtration combined with MF of tubular ceramic membrane and two step nano-filtration process after biological treatment using FM NP010 membrane under optimized conditions of pH, temperature and volume reduction factor (VRF) are best for treating paper mill effluent (Beril Gnder et al., 2011;

Pizzichini et al., 2005). NF270 membrane can be used for dilute and warm paper mill effluent, while UF has advantage of removing toxic substances and the biologically inactive substances but these face fouling problem(Kamali and Khodaparast, 2015; Maartens et al., 2002; Mänttari et al., 2004).

With low dosage of ozone in pre and post biological treatment, effluent biodegradability and reusability increases by complete detoxification and up to 90% COD removal(Hostachy et al., 1997).

Instead of tertiary treatment, the combined use of methods like Activated Sludge Process (ASP), Sequential Batch Reactor (SBR), Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (UASB), upflow anaerobic filter and Dissolved Air Flootation (DAF) can give effluent fit for reuse(Ashrafi et al., 2015; Žarković et al., 2011).

The problem of high molecular weight dissolved organic matter in pulp and paper mill effluent can be solved by electro-coagulation and adsorption [9]. The combined use of microfiltration and electro-dialysis results in water recovery of 90%(Nataraj et al., 2007). Moreover, desalination of wastewater makes it suitable for reuse in the processes with lesser cost than electrocoagulation(Madwar and Tarazi, 2003; Sridhar et al., 2011).

Various methods that can be used to treat pulp and paper wastewater to recycle quality are summarised in the Table 3.

Table 3. Methods to Treat Pulp and Paper Mills Wastewater

Treatment process	Results
Membrane-UF	50% colour removal, 55-87% COD removal, 35-44% BOD removal
DAF	97% TSS removal
Electrochemical method under optimized conditions	98% colour removal, 98% BOD removal, 97% COD removal
NF270 Nano-filtration membrane	80% Total dissolved carbon removal
MF (tubular ceramic membrane) and RO filtration	COD < 25ppm of O ₂ TOC = 1 mg/l, Conductivity = 70uS/cm 80% water saving
Ozonation and TiO ₂ - photocatalysis in addition to MBR	60% COD removal for kraft pulp mill, 35 % COD removal for recycled paper mill
Microfiltration and electro-dialysis	TDS = 546 mg/l, Conductivity = 0.6mS/cm, COD < 20mg/l 90% Water saving
Two step nano-filtration	91% COD removal, 92% hardness removal, 98% sulphate removal.

Coagulation and Flocculation with optimum dosing	82% water saving
Ozonation	Increase in effluent biodegradability
Closing water loop and using combination of micro and ultra-filtration	40% water saving

2.2 Mathematical and Graphical Methods

Application of mathematical methods on water networks for freshwater reduction should be followed by cost minimisation, productivity increase and ensuring quality of product (Jung and Pauly, 2011).

Mathematical Programming Based Methods

Non-Linear programming (NLP) supporting the water pinch involving assignment of integer variables to water consuming sections identifies major water users and gives cost effective output with 10% decrease in freshwater consumption(Alva-Argáez et al., 2007). Similarly, NLP model having input parameters as mass load, maximum inlet and outlet concentration of each contaminant in each water unit utilising, shortcomings of wastewater treatment and, decision variable as flow rates between different processes, presented minimum cost and flow reduction of 17.6% and maximum of 64.63% and 76.82% respectively(Faria et al., 2009).

Alternatively, by taking use of water from pulping/dilution process as constraints in mathematical model, regeneration cost and freshwater consumption can be minimized(Koppol et al., 2004). Likewise, two level optimization, first for total flow of fresh water and treatments, and second for minimizing total annualized cost including cost of installing treatment plant, freshwater cost and wastewater treatment costs can be done supported by mathematical modelling system General Algebraic Modeling System (GAMS)(Arzate et al., 2012).

Application of Multi-Objective distributed Q-learning (MDQL) for water and cost optimisation supported by applying reduced gradient method and combination of Unified Targeting Algorithm (UTA) for determination of minimum regeneration flow rate with Enhanced Nearest Neighbours Algorithm (NNA) and multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) minimizes water used, cost of chemical pulp and increases production efficiency by 4.7 m³ wood/ton of paper on an average(Alessandro et al., 2014; Mariano-Romero et al., 2007; Shenoy and Shenoy, 2015).

Graphical Methods

Plotting freshwater versus regeneration flowrate and outlet concentration diagrams along with savings versus investment diagram successfully minimises freshwater consumption and wastewater generation(Tan et al., 2007). Graphical method based on water pinch technology

reduces demineralised water by 25% and freshwater consumption by 60%(Zhang et al., 2016).

Combination of property integration technique, graphical and mathematical method with single contaminant approach gives water reduction of 43.8% for COD, 61.8 % for hardness and 39% for double contaminant(Mughees and Al-Ahmad, 2015).

Pinch Based Methods

One of the popular methods of optimising water use in industry is water-pinch methodology(Alva-Argáez et al., 2007) introduced by Wang and smith in 1994.

It can be used with water audit and membrane technologies(Agana et al., 2013), time dependant water cascade analysis and time-water network diagram(Wang et al., 2006). The methodology of maximum water-reuse and regeneration re-use analysis using WATER software respectively resulted in reduction of 22% and 30 % in fresh water consumption and its wastewater generation(Thevendiraraj et al., 2003). However, cost-effective minimum water network (CEMWN) reported that water pinch technology is useful for maximum water recovery and not for minimum water targets (Alwi et al., 2008).

Process integration of water pinch and mathematical programming for real time data collected for optimization of water circuit resulted in 23.2% reduction of water used(Hamaguchia and Parka, 2009). When used with chloride concentration as limiting constraint, it resulted in reduction of flow rates of freshwater by 57.5% and wastewater by 81.9%(Tian et al., 2008).

Simulation Based Methods

Minimisation of dissolved solids in bleaching plant effluent by substituting chlorine dioxide for chlorine can be done by simulation of bleach plant using FORTRAN program with process variables like residence time, consistency, bleaching liquor flow rate(Dogan and Guniz Guruz, 2004). Simultaneous water and energy optimization of brown stock washing system can also be done by analysing brown stock washing system mass balances in CADSIM simulation software(Chew et al., 2012). Simulation with control and optimization software reduces freshwater makeup in plant either by recycling or by reuse of water and treated wastewater(Panigrahi and Sharma, 2014).

Onsite Methods

Segregating of black liquor and subjecting it to chemical recovery(Tewari et al., 2009) and closing water loops in various sections then treating with membrane filtration(Mänttari et al., 2004) results in water conservation in paper mill. But closing of water loop causes large concentration of dissolved and colloidal inorganic and organic compounds(Žarković et al., 2011), scale deposits in boilers (calcite, barite and calcium oxalate) and bleach plants decreasing their efficiency(Huber et al., 2014).

Water auditing in process industry for identification of major water consuming and water losses areas, supplemented reuse of water within units and using alternate sources (like rainwater) resulted in water conservation(Barrington et al., 2013).

3. CASE STUDY: ON-SITE METHODS

An integrated Kraft based pulp and paper industry located in Central India is identified for the study. It has production capacity of 220 tons per day which includes paper, tissue and paperboard. The raw material used primarily consists of eucalyptus and recycled fibre. It takes water from a perennial river. The industry separates its process effluent into three classes based on degree of pollution and treats them separately. With the norms becoming more stringent and competition faced, the industry has adopted measures from time to time to cut down requirement of freshwater like separating separates its process effluent into three classes (chipper house, washing and paper machine) based on degree of pollution. But the industry needed further water conservation methods and techniques to reduce water consumption from current 100 m³/ton in order to have global stand.

3.1 Data Collection

The study collected data of water usage in the industry to attain objective of water conservation (Table 4.) and investigated on-site measures to reduce water demand of the industry.

Table 4. Water Usage in the Plant

Component	Value (m ³ /day)*
Water treatment plant intake	30000±2000
Freshwater consumption in the mill	22000±1600
Water supplied to drinking in nearby areas	7000
Loss of water/error in measurement	1000±200
Wastewater generation	17600±1500
Production(tons/day)	220
Section wise water consumption	
Pulp	5060±500
Paper, Tissue & Pilot plant	5280±700
Boiler	4400±300
Soda Recovery	7260±700

*range of values is due to seasonal variations

3.2 Results and Discussion

These measures with their approximate water reduction are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Section Wise Water Conservation

Water conservation measures	Section	Water Reduction (m ³)
Application of Bare Minimum technologies as listed in CPCB Charter 2015 and Remote Terminal Unit	Chipper house, Digester, Evaporator, Recovery boiler, Bleaching	270±80
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recycled water reuse in motor sealing and vacuum pump sealing and showers Tertiary treatment of wastewater and its reuse Closing water loop 	Paper, pulp, Wastewater Treatment Plant	760±200
Reducing water loss due to wind in Spray Pond Steam measurement and increasing condensate pit recovery	Boiler	780±140
Using recycled water in circulating water	Soda Recovery	2400±800
Treatment of Water Treatment Plant's sludge to recover water	Water Treatment Plant	340±60
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attending Minor & Major leakages Installation of advanced flow meters and leakage detectors Providing single tapping instead of multiple tappings & use of optimum diameter pipe 	Water distribution	630±150
Total		5180±600

Hence, the water consumption can be brought down to 16820m³ ± 1000m³ or 76.45 m³/ton of production from 100 m³/ton.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Numerous methods of water conservation and reuse that have been developed so far. These were studied on various industries along with pulp and paper industry. The mathematical programming methods and models with

software like CADSIM, GAMS, SCADA, PLC, MATLAB and WATER, that have achieved a great reduction in fresh water consumption and wastewater generation in industries having processes similar to pulp and paper industry, are needed to be used. Water audit, Water Balance and Water Source Diagram (WSD) with flow meters provide information about major water consuming areas as well as the losses incurred in the processes by spillage or leakage, which will help to save a huge amount of water. Advanced treatment methods provide a good quality effluent that can be recycled to the processes. But the methods have limitations in cost effectiveness. The optimisation of these methods by varying parameters can give acceptable results. Efficiency of membrane technologies vary from membrane to membrane. Selection of appropriate membrane or their combination gives satisfactory results. But the fouling and maintenance of membranes is a major issue. The development of new types of membranes will ensure ease in using them. The combination of mathematical programming with advanced methods of treatment will also result in reduction of freshwater consumption and wastewater generation. The use of primary and secondary treatment methods of aerobic and anaerobic type may remove the need of advanced treatment methods if worked out properly. Presented case study of a Kraft based Indian paper and pulp industry shows a reduction of about 23% in freshwater by adopting on-site methods. Moreover, further conservation in water can be achieved by adopting optimisation based methods as reviewed in the paper. Cost effective and site specific methods are yet to be developed for further water optimisation in the industry to meet water requirements and growing demand for paper in developing countries like India.

5. REFERENCES

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